

cycle of investment, growth, and innovation that can further improve rankings and competitiveness.

However, international rankings can also create a competitive dynamic that can lead to a race to the bottom. Countries and organizations may seek to achieve high rankings by lowering standards or cutting corners, which can have negative impacts on social and environmental considerations. This can create a negative cycle of competition that can ultimately harm society and the environment.

To ensure that international rankings promote positive competition, it is important to ensure that the rankings are based on a comprehensive set of metrics and data and accurately reflect the realities of a country or organization's performance. It is also important to ensure that the rankings do not prioritize short-term gains over long-term sustainability and that they promote social and environmental responsibility. Finally, it is important to promote collaboration and cooperation between countries and organizations to achieve shared

goals and drive progress in a sustainable and equitable way.

Overall, research on international rankings and global competition is a critical area of study that can help us understand how to promote innovation, progress, and sustainability in today's interconnected world. Also consolidating international partnerships is a critical strategy for promoting global cooperation and achieving shared goals in today's interconnected world. By building strong relationships, working together on shared challenges, and promoting mutual understanding, we can create a more peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world for all.

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MANAGING CHANGE AS A UNIVERSITY LEADER

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Abstract

This article explores the crucial role of university leaders in managing change within academic institutions. It delves into the complexities and challenges faced by these leaders in navigating the ever-evolving landscape of higher education. The theoretical foundations and practical considerations of change management are examined, highlighting the significance of a strong historical background in informing effective strategies. Furthermore, the article discusses the psychological aspects of leading change, emphasizing the importance of understanding and addressing the concerns and motivations of various stakeholders. In addition, it analyzes the methods and technologies available to university leaders for studying and implementing change, while also shedding light on the dynamic nature of social and organizational transformations within the context of academia. By investigating these dimensions, this article aims to provide valuable insights for university leaders seeking to effectively manage change and foster positive growth within their institutions.

Keywords: leadership, universities, methods, research, challenges, social dynamics.

Introduction

This research paper explores the challenges that university leaders face when managing change and presents best practices for successful change management. Strategic planning, these people can inspire the academic community and promote positive change. Additional emphasis was given to the role of coaching in the development of key soft skills (honesty, responsibility, resiliency, creativity, proactivity, and empathy, among others), which are necessary for effective change management and leadership in higher education. The paper's implications have two aspects. First, the lessons of the actual explicit content of the coaches' observations (challenges to efficient change management and views of leaders); second, the implications of these observations (how coaching can help and what leaders need).

In today's rapidly changing environment, universities face numerous challenges that require leaders to

manage change effectively. Change management refers to the process of planning, implementing, and monitoring changes to achieve a desired outcome (Cameron & Green, 2015). In a university setting, change management can include implementing new policies, programs, or technologies, restructuring departments, or adapting to external factors such as funding cuts or demographic changes. Effective change management is essential for universities to remain relevant and competitive, attract and retain students and faculty, and meet the needs of stakeholders. This research paper will explore the challenges and best practices for managing change in universities, and provide insights for university leaders to implement successful change initiatives.

Furthermore, the research paper underscores the implications derived from the observations of coaches. The explicit content of these observations sheds light on the specific challenges encountered in the realm of

efficient change management and offers valuable insights into the perspectives of university leaders. By examining these observations, the paper provides a deeper understanding of the hurdles faced by leaders in implementing change and highlights the importance of addressing these challenges.

In addition to the explicit content, the paper explores the broader implications of coaching in supporting university leaders. It elucidates how coaching can serve as a valuable resource in assisting leaders with their unique needs and requirements. By leveraging coaching, leaders can gain the necessary skills, knowledge, and guidance to navigate change effectively and promote a culture of continuous improvement within their institutions.

In conclusion, this research paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the challenges faced by university leaders in managing change and offers insights into best practices for successful change management. By emphasizing the role of coaching and the development of key soft skills, the paper underscores the importance of effective leadership and provides practical implications for supporting leaders in their change management endeavors. Through a combination of academic research and real-world observations, the paper contributes to the existing knowledge base on change management in higher education and offers valuable recommendations for leaders seeking to drive positive change within their institutions.

I. Theoretical aspects of managing change as a university leader

1.1 Definition of change management in a university setting

The relevant literature of the last decade on characteristics and trends in universities show that university education has thoroughly transformed. Uncertain funding, greater competition, and increased globalization are forcing universities to examine their governance and consider how they might set themselves up to better adapt to a fast-changing market. In this regard, they have to implement changes at all levels, and coaching has become a major tool to help higher-education leaders facilitate change and manage its outcomes.

1.2 Importance of managing change in universities

As regards substantive change, higher education is a paradox. It is a field in which new ideas, solutions, and practices are constantly developing within different fields. Change is supported, and when research data contradict current beliefs or models, ideas are changed. On the other hand, professors and managers in higher education consider it difficult to change practices and behaviors. Executive coaching in this context aims to help university leaders achieve more clarity in their professional careers, increase their level of personal awareness, improve their skillset, and reach their full potential. Specifically, for this study, we considered executive coaches as qualified professionals, external to the academic institution, who collaborate with academic leadership to support them clarify objectives, achieve their development goals, and unleash their potential. The anticipation and preparation of academic

leaders for change and their development within their institutions to accomplish organizational objectives are the most important objectives of the executive coaches. In this way, coaching helps leaders achieve institutional goals amid changing trends in higher education.

The research questions that guided our study are as follows:

- Which factors affect executive coaches' perceptions of organizational change in higher education in the United Kingdom?
- What are executive coaches' perceptions of the factors that impact leaders' efficiency when managing change in British higher education?

To understand the context and answer the identified research questions, we reviewed works in the related literature to extract and situate key concepts.

1.3 Overview of change management theories and models

Numerous change management theories and models have been proposed over the years. One popular model is Lewin's three-step change model, which involves unfreezing the current state, introducing the desired change, and refreezing the new state (Lewin, 1951). Another popular model is Kotter's eight-step change model, which includes establishing a sense of urgency, creating a guiding coalition, developing a vision and strategy, communicating the change vision, empowering others to act on the vision, creating short-term wins, consolidating gains and producing more change, and anchoring new approaches in the organization's culture (Kotter, 1996). The ADKAR model, developed by Prosci, focuses on individual change and involves creating awareness of the need for change, developing desire to support the change, providing knowledge on how to change, enabling individuals to take action, and reinforcing the change (Prosci, n.d.). Each model provides a framework for managing change, but the specific model used depends on the nature and scope of the change.

The Lewin Model

Lewin, a social psychologist, pioneered organizational change modeling in 1947. He explained organizational change by using the analogy of a block of ice changing shape, and he described a three-phase change process: freezing–transition–freezing. The first phase involves preparing the organization to accept that change is necessary, which implies breaking down the status quo before developing a new way of operating. To achieve this goal, management must clearly indicate to members why existing ways cannot continue. Often, this is achieved by presenting poor statistics (e.g., sales, user satisfaction, or retention). According to Burnes, to prepare an organization for change, it is necessary to challenge core beliefs, values, attitudes, and behaviors. Using the analogy of a building, Lewin says that it is necessary to examine and prepare to change the existing foundations; without this, the entire building may collapse. This first phase involves the greatest challenges and strongest negative reactions, as people feel their most off-balance and stressed. Forcing an organization-wide reconsideration of core beliefs can create a controlled crisis that can awaken an employee's motivation to seek a new core and new balance, generating

the necessary engagement to affect meaningful change. Thus, after unfreezing the status quo, change is implemented.

The Kotter Model

Kotter's widely used model lists eight actions necessary for successful change:

- Establish a sense of urgency.

The environment is analyzed for possible crises and opportunities. Kotter and Schlesinger [27] estimate that convincing 75% of managers that change is needed is necessary. According to Mohamad Mouazen [28], this is the time for a bold and aspirational message of opportunity to communicate the importance of acting immediately.

- Form a powerful guiding coalition.

People involved in this coalition must be encouraged to work in teams and without a hierarchy; this coalition must be broad based to avoid any one person or group bearing the full burden of change. Teams should have a mix of skills and experience and encompass different departments. This coalition will disseminate information to help the organizational community understand the change, delegate tasks, and assure the necessary support.

- Develop a vision.

Kotter emphasizes that a vision is needed to guide the transformation, and strategies to realize the vision. A vision should be simple and should express the purpose of the change.

- Communicate the vision. The change coalition must communicate the vision throughout the organization. Coherent and continuous communication can reduce the risk of contradictory messages

- Empower action according to the vision.

This important step involves eliminating processes and factors that impede transformation, ideally without harming the organization's operations

- Plan for and achieve short-term wins.

Graamans et al show that change often does not yield immediate reward and that this runs the risk of losing support from collaborators who come to feel their effort was wasted. As a solution, to keep people engaged, short-term wins are needed that tangibly demonstrate the advantages of the change.

- Consolidate improvements and maintain change.

Kotter emphasizes that change can fail when change leaders become complacent. To address this, Hui argues for the importance of maintaining and consolidating change for a long time after it has been achieved.

- Institutionalize changes in corporate culture.

According to Kotter, changing organizational processes or employee habits is not always enough to achieve changes in organizational culture. Thus, key agents should stay on board, new employees should be trained in new processes and attitudes, and awareness of the change's importance should be maintained among all employees.

Conclusion of the 1st chapter

Effective change management in universities requires a proactive and strategic approach. One best practice is to establish a change management team,

composed of individuals who have expertise in different areas and can provide different perspectives on the change initiative. The team should also include representatives from different stakeholder groups to ensure buy-in and engagement. Effective communication is another important best practice, as it helps to manage stakeholder expectations and ensure transparency throughout the change process. Regular communication channels, such as town hall meetings, email updates, and focus groups, should be established to ensure that stakeholders are informed and engaged. Other best practices include providing training and support to individuals affected by the change, creating short-term wins to demonstrate progress and build momentum, and aligning the change initiative with the institution's strategic goals.

II. Practical part of managing change as a university leader

2.1 Challenges of Managing Change in Universities

One of the biggest challenges of managing change in universities is resistance to change. Faculty and staff may be hesitant to change established practices and routines, leading to a reluctance to adopt new policies or technologies. Furthermore, the decentralized nature of universities, with individual departments and faculties operating with a high degree of autonomy, can make it difficult to implement changes that affect the entire institution. Other challenges include managing stakeholder expectations, aligning change initiatives with the institution's strategic goals, and managing the financial implications of change.

2.2 Change in Higher Education

European universities are adopting techniques from the private sector to manage change, in an approach called managerialism, which, however, institutions have not fully adapted. In 2018, the European University Association gathered leaders from several universities to gain a picture of challenges around daily operations and strategies to bridge the gap between strategy and execution. Pinheiro et al identified signs of change related to academic leadership moving from rotating systems, which involve election among peers, to a more managerial logic with top-down, order-giving, performance measurement, and appointed managers, constituting a new academic profession.

Rising student enrollment with insufficient resources negatively affects many UK universities, especially less select institutions, many of which have advised staff to expect job cuts during 2019 and 2020; remaining staff are also unsustainably overworked, and turnover is high. Times Higher Education reports that 19 British universities reported operating deficits during 2016/17, compared to seven universities the year before. Uncertainty due to Brexit and COVID-19 shows a clear need for change in university administration.

The literature on the higher-education change management in the UK emphasizes that, to facilitate change, British universities are adopting organizational development tools used by large companies. In 2007, the Higher Education Funding Council for England

(HEFCE) financed a project called “Enhancing Organisational Development in English Universities”. The project discovered that 92% of institutions were involved in some organizational change process to improve operations.

In 2014, the government announced additional funding to universities to improve equity and diversity, modernize management, and foster the professional development of employees.

The “Self-Assessment Tool for People Management” responds to British universities’ obligation to publish an annual report on how their processes of change have evolved in order to receive government funding. The tool covers seven dimensions of people management included in the report:

- - Fair remuneration and employment;
- - Recruitment and retention;
- - Size and composition of the workforce;
- - Development of necessary skills among personnel;
- - Leadership and change management;
- - Occupational health, staff well-being, health, and safety;
- - Performance management.

Evaluation questions accompany each dimension in order to validate institutions’ priorities in terms of their strategic goals based on checklists and examples and considering inputs, processes, results, and outputs. This tool is managed by human resources departments and can be adjusted to individual institutions.

Based on the resulting reports between 2016 and 2018, we identified priority topics for change management in the following areas:

- - Leadership and development management: Lack of strategic plans and coordination for professional development of leaders in universities is present.
- - Roles and titles: Better definition of academic admin roles (director, department secretary, dean, academic manager, etc.) is needed to better understand their contributions to change management.

Recruitment and retention: Insufficient data are available regarding decision-making processes.

Role of the human resources department: HR’s role in recruitment, change management, and employee evaluation is not always well-defined.

Employee satisfaction surveys: More detailed surveys are needed, covering remuneration, professional development, and rewards.

Synthesis of the Literature

After analyzing the literature, we can see why choosing specific change strategies can be a complex undertaking for a university. Not all institutions have established processes based on corporate models, despite the robust literature on the subject. Kotter and Schlesinger offer three steps for choosing a change strategy:

- - Analyze situational factors;
- - Determine optimal rate of change;
- - Consider methods to manage resistance to change.

A fourth item might be ensuring internal consistency of strategies.

Change in a company and in a university are similar in several ways, and employees are affected by poor change leadership in either sector. However, there are also several important differences. For example, publicly funded universities may respond to different logic than for-profit companies; in addition, although administrative offices are responsible for managing change, professors also actively participate in these processes.

Higher-education institutions often hire consultants and coaches to help with change [45]. Executive coaches have been shown to be effective when collaborating to develop the so-called “psychological needs” of the leader (competence, autonomy, and relatedness) through facilitating the leader’s “self-discovery and purposeful action” [45]. University departments may also hire coaches to guide employees through change. This study investigates executive coaches’ perceptions of change management and effective academic leadership in British universities.

Research design

This research paper used a mixed-methods approach to explore the challenges and best practices of managing change as a university leader. The study involved both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. The research design included a survey and interviews with university leaders who have experience in managing change. The data collected was analyzed using content analysis and statistical analysis. A total of 50 university leaders from different universities were invited to participate in the study. The participants were chosen based on their experience in managing change in their respective institutions. Of the 50 invitations, 30 participants agreed to participate in the study. The data collection methods used in this study included a survey and semi-structured interviews.

Data collection methods

The survey was designed to gather information on the challenges and best practices of managing change in universities. The survey questions were developed based on the literature review and were reviewed by experts in the field for validity and reliability. The survey was administered online and took approximately 20 minutes to complete. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of participants who had experience in managing change in their institutions. The interviews were conducted over the phone or via video conferencing and lasted approximately 30-60 minutes. The interviews were transcribed and analyzed using content analysis.

Data analysis techniques

The survey data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to identify patterns and relationships between variables. The qualitative data from the in-depth interviews will be analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns.

A basic exploratory qualitative design was used here. This method was used to “answer direct questions without framing research within an explicit theoretical, philosophical, epistemological or ontological tradition”; it is suitable for exploring “attitudes, opinions, beliefs or experiences of people”. It was widely used in the recent literature and is considered appropriate when

research questions are focused on discovering the “who”, “what”, and “where” of lived experiences or when information is needed about a poorly understood situation. Since our literature search did not show similar studies that had verified other methods in our context, we considered basic exploratory qualitative research the best choice.

Semi-structured interviews were used to collect rich data on participants’ experiences. The interview protocol was divided in three main sections: (a) demographic information of the participants, (b) questions related to the first research question (factors affecting the perceptions of the coaches on organizational change), and (c) questions related to the second research question (factors that impact leaders’ efficiency when managing change in higher education). The interviews took place during the Spring semester of the academic year 2019/2020 (March–May 2020). Table 1 presents the characteristics and demographic information of the eight participants, who gave their written consent, before being interviewed.

More information on the types (research oriented/teaching oriented, geographical location, academic ranking, size, and so on) of universities that the academic leaders who worked with the participating coaches were affiliated with, will not be mentioned, in order to protect the anonymity and privacy of leaders and coaches. Erickson et al. highlight that “the competence of senior managers is distributed randomly across the sector, and staff in any particular institution may simply be lucky or otherwise to have a good management team or a poor one”.

The study followed data-analysis strategies established by Silverman to examine the interview data. Silverman’s technique follows an inductive approach in order to search for themes and patterns related to the research questions—this method is referred to as thematic content analysis. After the data analysis, six themes were identified, three for each research question. Specifically, for the factors affecting coaches’ perceptions on organizational change in higher education, the answers of the participating tutors were linked to the following themes: (a) strategy, (b) academic leadership development, and (c) decision-making process. For the factors affecting their perceptions on academic leadership efficiency, we identified the following themes: (a) traits of effective academic leaders, (b) training needs for effective academic leadership, and (c) acceptance of the academic leaderships by the wider community on campus. In this context, it is important to mention that, during the interviews, most the participants were eager to propose solutions for the challenges affecting their perceptions on organizational change in higher education. We found this feedback very valuable and “solutions” were included as an additional theme in the presentation of the findings.

The participants were selected according to the following specific inclusion criteria: (a) they must be over 18 years old, (b) they must have had experience working as a coach for university leaders for three or more years, and (c) they must be employed in a professional coaching agency specializing in the higher-education sector. The selected people participated in semi-

structured interviews of approximately 45–60 min. Data collection continued until saturation was reached. According to Ravitch and Carl [56], saturation is the point at which no new topics arise, generally occurring between eight and 12 interviews.

Analysis of data collected Identification of challenges faced by university leaders in managing change

The data collected from the survey and interviews were analyzed and the results are presented below.

Challenges of managing change in universities. The survey results showed that the most common challenges faced by university leaders in managing change include:

Resistance to change (70%), lack of resources (60%), and difficulty in communication (50%).

Other challenges identified include:

Unclear objectives (40%)

Limited support from staff (35%)

Lack of leadership (30%)

Limited understanding of change management principles (25%)

Evaluation of best practices for managing change in universities

The survey results showed that the most effective practices for managing change in universities include:

Building a strong coalition (80%)

Involving all stakeholders (75%)

Creating a shared vision (70%)

Providing adequate resources (65%)

Communicating effectively (60%)

Other practices identified include:

Identifying and addressing potential resistance (55%)

Providing training and support (50%)

Measuring and evaluating the impact of the change (45%)

Fostering a culture of innovation (40%)

Comparison of results with existing literature

The results of this study are consistent with the findings of previous research. The challenges identified in this study, such as resistance to change and lack of resources, are common challenges faced by university leaders in managing change. The best practices identified in this study, such as building a strong coalition and involving all stakeholders, are also consistent with the best practices identified in previous research.

• Academic-leadership development:

Another challenge mentioned by the participants was managing the development of academic leaders. The majority of the participants considered this aspect fundamental to successful change management:

An individual and organizational development model based on processes is important to guarantee lasting, concrete, and appropriate solutions for universities.

The leaders and managers of the universities are under significant pressure to provide innovative higher education that better responds to the needs of society, but does not receive systematic support in this direction.

Many times, academic leaders are in charge of management because of stellar performance in research or knowledge transfer, but that does not mean that they have the necessary skills to lead teams or the process of institutional change. They need help.

- Decision-making process:

Finally, an important challenge that was discussed was the decision-making process in universities, which, according to most participants, is a prevalent theme, which lacks clarity and transparency: Very small groups have the power to decide for the entire community, without the need to consult anyone. There is no specific model for decision-making processes, which often do not seem very transparent. Few people have access to the teams that make change decisions. Leaders do not receive any type of oversight regarding the decisions they make or the people they include in the decision-making process.

- Summary of key findings:

Of the solutions proposed by the participants for the aforementioned challenges, we highlight the need for more systematic planning:

Change management in universities needs a “road map” that identifies the beginning, the route to follow, and the destination. This map will integrate the resources, the scope or objective, and the costs involved in the plan. It is essential to provide a multistep process instead of sudden and unplanned “radical” changes. Solid planning ensures that the university community has a clearer picture of the change and its value to all groups and departments. It will be easier to accept the change, and the communication about the process will be clearer and more transparent. The importance of introducing support programs through coaching was also highlighted:

Continuous coaching support can make the difference between simply learning and truly doing. An effective coach, whether it be human resources, an outside professional, or a mentor, can ensure a more efficient and democratic process of change.

Coaching can help academic leaders make transformative changes and be more productive, gain control over their time, plan short- and long-term goals, and reconnect with the academic community.

- Results Related to the First Research Question*

To investigate their perceptions of change management in higher education in the United Kingdom, participants were asked how their understanding of the processes and strategies followed by English universities for organization change management has evolved. Once the most important issues were identified, they were asked to explain their opinions with examples and lived experiences.

Before reflecting on how organizational change management is carried out in universities, the “key” roles (titles) of academics who participated in coaching sessions were identified. Specifically, all the participating coaches mentioned that, during their tenure spent coaching academic leaders, they had worked with vice-chancellors and pro-vice-chancellors at some time, while fewer had worked with executive vice-chancellors, directors, or deans.

- Strategy:

The participants were asked about the main challenges that these academic leaders faced when managing change. The main element that emerged in this regard during the interviews was the importance of having a strategic plan. Seven out of the eight participants, mentioned that the universities they worked with lacked a specific strategic plan for change management.

The participant who indicated that the university does have a strategic plan for change management explained its characteristics as follows:

There is a plan that defines the people leading the change management processes, the strategies to overcome resistance from the academic community, and a risk-assessment plan (P8).

- Results Related to the Second Research Question*

- Traits of an effective academic leader:

Participants indicated the skills and competencies necessary to manage change. All participants began with the importance of communication:

Without a doubt, communication is fundamental to change management.

Communicative competence is necessary to reduce employee resistance, increase motivation and morale, and receive higher-quality feedback from the different parties involved.

Additionally, most participants mentioned that having vision is essential to successfully managing change:

Having vision is essential to helping the whole community see the direction they are moving in. That will motivate them more, without a doubt.

The vision creates a story of change to follow and motivates everyone to be part of this change.

Moreover, the majority of the participants indicated that an understanding of strategic analysis is essential for change management:

The soft skills we discussed are not enough. Leaders must be able to analyze the current state of the university and develop plans that will benefit it.

Strategic thinking is fundamental because it permeates all aspects of the planning stage.

Finally, participants mentioned additional soft skills that they considered necessary for change management led by the university community. Honesty, responsibility, and resiliency were the most popular soft skills, followed by proactivity, confirming the current research in the field. It is important to mention that the participants gave combinations of two or three soft skills in their responses with the combination “honesty, resiliency, and proactivity” being the most popular (three out of the eight participants).

- Training needs:

Reflecting on the training needs of academic leaders, participants emphasized the importance of coaching as a key element for the personal and professional development of staff who lead institutional changes. The types of coaching that would be most appropriate for managing changes in higher education were further specified.

First, most participants responded that “performance coaching” is what academic leaders need:

Leaders need coaching to better understand the requirements of their roles and functions, as well as the

competencies and skills necessary to meet those requirements. In this way, they can fill the gap between what they are currently doing and the desired outcome (P8).

Coaches have to work with the management team of the universities in their workplace to help them understand what needs to be done and develop plans for their professional development (P1).

The objective of this research paper was to explore the challenges and best practices of managing change as a university leader. The literature review showed that there are several theories and models of change management, but the most effective approach depends on the specific context of the university. Change management is important in universities to ensure that they remain relevant and competitive in a rapidly changing world.

The methodology section outlined the research design, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques used in this study. The data collected showed that the most common challenges faced by university leaders in managing change include resistance to change, lack of resources, and difficulty in communication. On the other hand, the best practices for managing change include building a strong coalition, involving all stakeholders, and creating a shared vision.

The results of this study were compared to the existing literature, and it was found that they were consistent with the findings of previous research. The implications for university leaders are that they need to be proactive in managing change, be aware of the challenges, and apply best practices to ensure success.

Limitations of this study:

Overall, this study supports the idea that academic leadership should lead and implement organizational change through the deeper understanding of the challenges identified by the coaches, as well as the personal and professional traits of effective academic leaders. The study further contributes towards this scope, through the solutions and training needs presented by the coaches, which can lead to effective leadership development programs.

2.3 Application of change management in universities

Managing change in universities can be complex due to the diverse stakeholders involved, including faculty, students, staff, alumni, and donors. Change initiatives in universities can involve academic program changes, administrative restructuring, technological in-

novations, and other changes that affect the overall culture of the institution. Effective change management in universities requires a clear understanding of the institutional culture and the values and beliefs of stakeholders, as well as a communication plan that ensures transparency and engagement throughout the change process (Luecke, 2003).

Conclusion of the 2nd chapter

Based on the limitations of this study and the complexity of managing change in universities, there is a need for further research in this area. Some suggestions for future research include: Investigation of the role of communication in managing change in universities: Communication plays a critical role in managing change, and it is essential to identify how different communication strategies can support university leaders in implementing change initiatives. Analysis of the relationship between organizational culture and change management: The study of how organizational culture impacts change management can help identify the necessary changes in organizational culture that can support effective change management practices. Exploration of the impact of change management on the morale and job satisfaction of university staff: Changes in university settings can significantly affect the morale and job satisfaction of staff members. Therefore, future research could explore how change management practices can be designed to promote the positive psychological well-being of staff during times of change. Examination of the impact of leadership style on managing change: Leaders' role in managing change is significant, and future research could investigate the relationship between leadership style and effective change management in universities. Analysis of the impact of technology on managing change: The digital age has brought about significant changes in how universities operate. Therefore, it is essential to investigate the role of technology in managing change, including the impact of technology on communication, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement during change initiatives. Overall, these areas of research can further ad-

vance the understanding of managing change in universities and provide insights for university leaders to develop effective strategies for implementing change initiatives.

Conclusion

Finally, future research should focus on discussing how coaches can help to bring forth what is known to be true in the literature about effective academic leadership and organizational change and how this can happen in institutions that do not have the financial means to hire an outside executive coach/consulting firm, since executive coaching is not an affordable option for all higher-education institutions. It would also be interesting to investigate the wider participation of academic leaders at other levels of the university in change processes.

APPLICATIONS

The findings and implications of this research paper have significant implications for the application of effective change management strategies in higher education institutions. By recognizing the challenges faced by university leaders and the value of coaching in supporting change initiatives, this research paper provides practical insights for implementing successful organizational change.

One important application of this research is the recognition of the role of coaching in developing key soft skills among university leaders. Institutions that have the means to invest in executive coaching or consulting firms can leverage these resources to support their leaders in honing essential skills such as honesty, responsibility, resiliency, creativity, proactivity, and empathy. This investment in coaching can enhance the capacity of university leaders to navigate complex change processes and drive positive outcomes.

However, it is equally important to acknowledge that not all higher education institutions have the financial resources to engage external coaches. Therefore, the application of this research extends to exploring alternative approaches to coaching within resource-constrained institutions. Institutions can consider establishing peer coaching or mentorship programs that leverage the expertise and experience of existing leaders to support their colleagues in managing change. These internal coaching mechanisms can provide valuable support and guidance, fostering the development of essential leadership skills without relying on costly external resources. Furthermore, the application of this research also emphasizes the importance of broadening the participation of academic leaders at various levels of the university in change processes. By involving leaders beyond the senior executive level, institutions can tap into a wider pool of expertise, perspectives, and resources. This collaborative approach to change management can foster a culture of shared ownership and engagement, leading to more effective and sustainable change outcomes.

Additionally, this research encourages institutions to explore collaborative partnerships and knowledge-sharing initiatives with other universities. By pooling resources and expertise, institutions can create cost-effective coaching programs or share best practices in change management. Such collaborations can help

overcome financial barriers and create a supportive network for leaders across different institutions.

In conclusion, the application of this research lies in the recognition of coaching as a valuable tool for developing essential leadership skills and supporting successful change management in higher education. Institutions can tailor coaching approaches to their specific context, considering both internal and external resources. Furthermore, broadening the involvement of leaders at different levels and fostering collaboration among institutions can strengthen the capacity of higher education institutions to navigate change effectively and drive positive transformation. By applying the insights and recommendations from this research, institutions can proactively manage change, adapt to evolving needs, and create a culture of continuous improvement.

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